

Interview with child before experiment:

Overall instructions for interviewers;

- Explain the purpose of the interview:
 - o To gather information about their experience with the PAL system
 - o To use this information to change and improve the PAL system
 - o It is not a test, so no wrong or right answers and criticism (if you did not like something, or like to see something improved) is greatly valued
- Ask for permission to audio tape the conversation
- Try to complete the following questionnaire with the child.
- Encourage the child to elaborate, and try to think of follow up questions, especially when the answer is not clear (write down the main aspects of their answer)

QUESTIONS ROBOT PERCEPTION BEFORE

Which of the following 6 pictures best displays a robot according to your opinion?

Please circle the robot that according to you best resembles a “robot”.

Imagine that you are a robot builder who is being asked to build a robot.
What would you do: what would you want the robot to be able to do?

.....

.....

.....

Have you met a robot before?

No / Yes, why and where:

.....

.....

Please choose the word that best describes a robot in your opinion:

You can only choose one word:

- A machine
- A friend, a pal
- A teacher: somebody or something that explains things
- A cuddly toy: something cute
- A technical toy
- A helper: somebody or something that helps others

What do you expect of the robot?

You can only choose one answer:

- That he can play with me
- That he understands me
- That he can help me with my diabetes
- That he can talk with me
- That he can teach me useful things
- That we learn useful things together
- Nothing
- Other, namely:

According to you, a robot is able to:

- | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|---------------------------|-----------------------------|--------------------------|
| - To talk or communicate with someone | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - To move | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - To show emotions | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - To recognize emotions of others | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - To remember or recall things | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - To see me | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - To understand me | <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> Maybe | <input type="radio"/> No |
| - Other, namely: | | | |

Motivation & Expectations	Very untrue		A bit true		Very true
	1	2	3	4	5
I am looking forward to playing with the robot in the hospital					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think that playing with the robot in the hospital will be boring					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think I have enough skills to play with the robot in the hospital					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think I have enough time to play with the robot in the hospital					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I expect that playing with the robot in the hospital will help me with my diabetes					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I am looking forward to playing with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet at home					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think that playing with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet at home will be boring					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think I have enough skills to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet at home					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think I have enough time to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet at home					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I expect that playing with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet will help me with my diabetes					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I think I have enough time to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet at home					

Remarks:					
I participate in this study because I want to for myself					
Remarks:					
I participate in this study because my parents and/or the nurse want me to					
Remarks:					

Use of technology before:

	Is it yours?		How many often do you use it/week?				With whom do you use it?		
	Yes	No	Never	Once a week	Once a day	More than once a day	Alone	With parents	With friends
smartphone 									
tablet 									
computer/laptop 									
game computer/console 									

If child has a smart phone (or if they can use parents' smart phone):

How often do you use the internet on your smart phone when you are not home?

Never Once a week Once a day More than once a day

Which games or apps do you like most on the smart phone?

1.
2.
3.

Which activities do you like most on the smart phone? Think of talking on the phone, making pictures, sharing pictures, chatting (Whatsapp), Social Network (Facebook/Twitter), playing games etc.

1.
2.
3.

Which activities do you like most on the internet? Think of reading, searching for information, looking at videos, chatting, social networks (facebook/twitter), listening to music, playing online games.

1.
2.
3.

Do you sometimes use the internet to search for information about Diabetes?

No / Yes: what kind of information:

.....
.....

Knowledge & goals Before

- Can you explain which illness you have and what you have to do?
- Do you prick your glucose by yourself?
- Do you interpret the value yourself or do you discuss the value with your parents?
- Can you explain the influence of insulin, carbohydrates and exercise on your blood glucose?
- Have you experienced a low blood sugar yet? What are the symptoms and what should you do when you get a low blood sugar / What should you do when you do not feel well?
(Answer: alert an adult)
- How do you inject your insulin? What role do your parents play?
- How do you deal with eating certain foods? What role do your parents play?
- Can you explain the relationship between nutrition, insulin and physical activity?

Goal that will be worked on the coming month: To be set with nurse/doctor

Please complete the **PEDSQL questionnaire** with the child

Interview with child during the experiment (telephonic 15 minutes):

- Overall: how is it going?
- How is it going with goal that has been set?
- Did you experience any problems?
- Per functionalities of System: how did it go with uploading photo's, uploading glucose values, playing quiz etc.?
- How often did you used until now? For on average how long each time?
- What do you think about the robot on you mobile phone tablet?
 - o Is it difficult to use?
 - o What do you think about the way it looks?
 - o Do you need of assistance from your parents?
- Can you think of anything that could be improved?
 - o If not, could you think about what can be improved, during the coming days before you return to the hospital.
 - o If yes, could you think about what more can be improved, during the coming days before you return to the hospital.

Thank you for your time!

Interview with child after experiment:

Overall instructions for interviewers;

- Explain the purpose of the interview:
 - o To gather information about their experience with the PAL system
 - o To use this information to change and improve the PAL system
 - o It is not a test, so no wrong or right answers and criticism (if you did not like something, or like to see something improved) is greatly valued
- Ask for permission to audio tape the conversation
- Try to complete the following questionnaire with the child.
- Encourage the child to elaborate, and try to think of follow up questions, especially when the answer is not clear (write down the main aspects of their answer)

Knowledge & goals After

- Can you explain which illness you have and what you have to do?
- Do you prick your glucose by yourself?
- Do you interpret the value yourself or do you discuss the value with your parents?
- Can you explain the influence of insulin, carbohydrates and exercise on your blood glucose?
- Have you experienced a low blood sugar yet? What are the symptoms and what should you do when you get a low blood sugar / What should you do when you do not feel well?
(Answer: alert an adult)
- How do you inject your insulin? What role do your parents play?
- How do you deal with eating certain foods? What role do your parents play?
- Can you explain the relationship between nutrition, insulin and physical activity?

Questions interaction with robot	Very untrue		A bit true		Very true	
	1	2	3	4	5	
When I meet the robot in the hospital I feel that I am free to do what I want						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I am not very good at playing the quiz with the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I like playing with the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I like the robot I have met in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
Ask the child whether (s)he used his/her mobile phone or tablet to play with the robot at home to						

adjust the following questions accordingly:

When I meet the robot on my mobile phone or tablet I feel that I am free to do what I want.					
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Remarks:

I am not very good at playing the quiz with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Remarks:

I like playing with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Remarks:

I like the robot when he appears on my mobile phone or tablet					
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Remarks:

The next questions are about the robot in general

The robot decides what I should do					
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Remarks:

The robot really likes me					
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Remarks:

I have learned a lot of new things while playing the quiz with the robot					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Remarks:

I have learned a lot of new things while telling him of my activities on my mobile phone or tablet					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Remarks:

The robot helped me with accomplishing the goal that I have set with the nurse					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Remarks:

I think of the robot as a friend					
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Remarks:

I think of the robot as a teacher					
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Remarks:

I think of the robot as a nurse or doctor					
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Remarks:

How did you feel while playing with the robot in the hospital?

Can you explain why?

How did you feel while playing with the robot on your mobile phone or tablet?

Can you explain why?

What did you like most of the robot in the hospital?

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What did you like least of the robot in the hospital?

.....

What did you like most of the robot on you mobile phone or tablet?

.....

What did you like least of the robot on you mobile phone or tablet?

.....

QUESTIONS ROBOT PERCEPTIONS AFTER

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According to you, a robot is able to:

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| - Other, namely: | | | |

Questions user experience	Very untrue		A bit true		Very true	
	1	2	3	4	5	
I would like to continue to meet and play with the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
It was difficult for me to play with the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I sometimes got confused when I played with the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
It was difficult for me to understand how I could play with the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I liked the way appearance the robot in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I was very much looking forward to meeting the robot again in the hospital						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I would like to continue to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet and tell him about my activities						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
It was difficult for me to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
I need the support of my parents to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
The robot in the hospital and the robot on my mobile phone or tablet are the same						
<i>Remarks:</i>						
It was difficult for me to understand how I could play and talk						

with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I sometimes got confused when I played with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I liked the appearance of the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I like the appearance of the app on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
Sometimes I did not feel like talking to the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I was very much looking forward to talking to the robot again on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I sometimes got bored while playing with the robot in the hospital					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I sometimes got bored while playing with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
<i>The next questions are about the robot in general</i>					
I trust the robot					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
The robot helped me with my diabetes					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
The robot helped me with accomplishing my goals					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
The robot helped me to perform better in daily life (school, sports)					
<i>Remarks:</i>					

I felt supported by the robot in dealing with my diabetes					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
The robot helped in to perform the activities I have to do to manage / for my diabetes					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
My parents think I should play with the robot					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
The nurse and doctor think I should play with the robot					
<i>Remarks:</i>					
I do not have enough time to play with the robot on my mobile phone or tablet					
<i>Remarks:</i>					

How often did you play or talk with the robot on your mobile phone or tablet:

- Once a week
- Twice a week
- Every other day
- Every day

On average how long did you play with the robot on your mobile phone or tablet?

- 5 minutes
- 10 minutes
- 20 minutes
- 30 minutes
- More than 30 minutes

Would you have preferred to play with the robot in the hospital O more/ O less often?

Would you have preferred to play with the robot on your mobile phone or tablet O more/ O less often?

Can you think of ways that can the robot better help you better or be improved?
Eg. Other appearance or options, Help you with you diabetes, Help you perform better, Support you in dealing with diabetes.

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